

1 News/Views article:

2 **Title:**

3 **How can regulation and reimbursement better accommodate flexible**
4 **suites of digital health technologies?**

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12 **Abstract**

13 **Individual digital health devices are increasingly being bundled together as interacting,**
14 **multicomponent suites, to deliver clinical services (e.g., teleconsultation and ‘hospital-at-**
15 **home services’). In the first article of this two-article series we described the challenges**
16 **in implementation and the current limitations in frameworks for the regulation, health**
17 **technology assessment, and reimbursement of these device suites and linked novel care**
18 **pathways. A flexible and fit-for-purpose evaluation framework that can analyze the**
19 **strengths and weaknesses of digital technologies suites is needed. In this second article**
20 **we describe adaptations that could enable this new technological paradigm while**
21 **maintaining patient safety and fair value.**

22

23 **[MAIN]**

24 The delivery of healthcare is evolving to incorporate digital health technology (DHT) with a
25 rise in interacting systems of DHT suites, characterized by modularity, embedding,
26 aggregation, adaptability, co-design, and rapid evolution. This ongoing transformation has
27 led to a shift from conventional face-to-face patient-clinician interactions to telemedicine
28 approaches that incorporate aspects of remote health care provider (HCP) management of
29 patients, the greater use of wireless sensor technologies for measuring patient physiology,
30 and the merging of these concepts through the inclusion of aspects of automation, machine
31 decision making and even advice¹. This entails the exchange of patient data, data and
32 algorithm-driven practices, and distributed trust extending beyond traditional healthcare
33 practices². Our previous article³ in this two-article series, described how there is much
34 enthusiasm for the potential of these suite-based workflows to positively transform care,
35 alongside substantial challenges in their regulation, health technology assessment (HTA),
36 and reimbursement. Frameworks are unsurprisingly playing catch up with these fast-evolving
37 technologies. Some device suites are specifically developed for aggregated use.
38 Increasingly, individually approved 'standalone' DHTs, which may even have 'standalone'
39 HTA and reimbursement recommendations, can be brought together on an ad hoc basis.
40 Understandably, current evaluation frameworks focus on individual DHTs rather than on
41 integrated systems or bundles. The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) commissioner
42 Robert Califf directly acknowledged this in a February 2024 speech, saying "If you think
43 about device development, like sensors, if you do it one at a time, you'll never put a whole
44 suite together into something that fits together in the [home] environment. [The FDA is]
45 working on a strategy on how to create regulatory pathways to help make that happen"⁴.
46 A range of different types of DHT aggregations are possible for which differing regulatory
47 and HTA considerations apply. Some of these suites are well established, and some exist

48 more as concepts described in the literature rather than as approaches currently adopted in
49 mainstream healthcare (**Table 1**). We describe the need for change in current frameworks,
50 and describe approaches that could be applied for this relatively new phenomenon.

51

52 [Table 1]

53

54 **Regulatory considerations for aggregates of DHTs**

55 It is rational that medical device regulation frameworks require developers to consider the
56 interactions between their devices and other devices that they are planned to directly interact
57 with⁹. In former eras, it is likely that the developer could anticipate all future uses and DHT
58 interactions. Although this approach may have seemed logical and balanced at the time of
59 writing the laws, the increasing networked interaction of DHTs now falls short in addressing
60 the complexities of modern mobile communications systems. While we recognize that
61 communication systems originated in low-risk environments compared to healthcare, to keep
62 pace with advancing digital progress a cautious introduction of systems with safeguards to
63 identify unintended consequences early on, could be necessary. This approach prioritizes
64 dynamic monitoring and evidence generation over aversion to technology, promoting optimal
65 and safe healthcare practices without advocating for a free-for-all system.

66

67 As highlighted in **Table 1**, it is highly challenging to define a taxonomy for suites of devices.
68 There is need for understanding both from the manufacturer's and regulator's side to strike a
69 balance that is proportionate to risk. In this complex environment, transparency is key and
70 requires to be noted by both parties. Manufacturers have the responsibility to make data
71 available data and conduct trend reporting for real-world performance monitoring to ensure
72 patient safety. The pandemic recognized the need for aggregation of individual DHTs into
73 service bundles but without systematic and automated monitoring that can now be achieved.

74 Flexible monitoring ideas, like integrated collection of feedback from system users (patients
75 and HCPs), can support this effort ^{1,10}.

76

77 **The need for a flexible way forward in HTA evaluation of DHT aggregates**

78 Just as regulation needs to adopt a more flexible approach to governing interacting DHT
79 systems, the same adaptability is necessary for HTA and reimbursement processes. There
80 is currently no comprehensive assessment framework to evaluate DHTs in general, let alone
81 modular DHT suites that function independently or in an aggregated system. Current DHT
82 assessment approaches, which are based on care processes, could evolve to be system-
83 based. For example, in Belgium, authorized digital health applications may receive
84 reimbursement as part of a healthcare process, receiving a lump sum for treatment rather
85 than individual reimbursements for specific actions¹¹. This model can be applied to modular
86 digital health tools, reimbursing them as part of a whole system instead of as individual
87 components.

88

89 Another route to promote innovation in healthcare technology was adopted by Germany
90 proposing the digital health application (DiGA) fast-track system that allowed temporary
91 reimbursement, during a one-year evidence generation period, and this did achieve its aim¹².
92 There were also drawbacks - full reimbursement was provided to many DiGAs that later did
93 not prove positive benefits¹³, but soon to be enforced rules on ongoing performance
94 monitoring, bring promise of a fair balance of early reimbursement and promotion of
95 innovation¹⁴. Our view is that the described model could be extended to the provisional
96 approval of integrated DHT suites, allowing temporary approvals and partial reimbursement,
97 while sharing risks with manufacturers until benefits are proven. To deliver safety, it would
98 be essential to ensure that: (i) manufactures define an 'envelope' for the safe use of their
99 device – which may not predict every device combination but delineates permissible use
100 types, such as suitability for critical monitoring; and, (ii) the registration of new combinations

101 and use cases as they are identified; and, (iii) the testing of new use cases and
102 combinations promptly, automatically gathering feedback on use where possible¹ and with
103 the requirement for manufactures to risk assess and gather surveillance data.

104

105 **Summary**

106 We advocate for better recognition in regulations and HTA frameworks that DHTs can be
107 aggregated into modular suites, expanding beyond discrete purposes. Here the individual
108 device intended purposes may form a guide but should not be a barrier to use in wider,
109 combinatory use cases. Why is this needed? Nations will get the digital care futures they
110 legislate for, regulate for and choose through reimbursement decisions. To enable
111 transformational benefit through new care paradigms that are possible through digital
112 medicine, a first step is the acknowledgment and readiness for change. Under-cautious
113 approaches could lead to unsafe technologies. Regulatory, HTA and reimbursement
114 approaches based on traditional concepts of discrete DHTs, are unlikely to realize the
115 comprehensive benefits of digital transformation. Countries adopting flexible approval,
116 assessment, and payment frameworks, coupled with robust and intelligent oversight, are
117 likely to achieve digitally transformed medical technologies suited to societal needs, reducing
118 costs, environmental impact, and enhancing quality of care.

119

120 **Contributions**

121 S.G. developed the concept of the manuscript. R.M. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. R.M.,
122 P.M., A.C. and S.G. contributed to the writing, interpretation of the content, and editing of the
123 manuscript, revising it critically for important intellectual content. R.M., P.M., A.C. and S.G. had
124 final approval of the completed version. R.M., P.M., A.C. and S.G. take accountability for all
125 aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of
126 the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

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129 **Competing interests**

130 R.M and P.M. declare no nonfinancial interests and no competing financial interests. S.G.
131 declares a nonfinancial interest as an Advisory Group member of the EY-coordinated “Study on
132 Regulatory Governance and Innovation in the field of Medical Devices” conducted on behalf of
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139 Ada Health GmbH and holds share options in Ada Health GmbH. S.G. is a News and Views
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156 **Table legends**

157 **Table 1. Examples of aggregated suites of DHTs in healthcare.** The suites are described,
158 along with examples of the medical settings, applications, and workflows in which they are
159 used. The regulatory status of example DHT suites are summarized as is their most common
160 treatment in HTA and reimbursement. There is significant overlap between categories, with the
161 main difference currently being the regulatory techniques adopted by manufacturers, often due
162 to ambiguity rather than technical variations between products. MD: Medical device, HCP:
163 Health care provider, HAH: Hospital at Home, EHR: Electronic Health Record.

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#	Description of functional aggregate of DHTs	Example system or service	Usual regulatory and HTA status of system
1	Single manufacturer developed system of DHTs, as interacting components of a system, each with individual MD approval or MD approval as a single system, together designed to interact to deliver a specific function.	An implanted pacemaker (modern forms of which combines DHT interactivity with an older closed-loop stimulator concept) has interaction with: (i) remote monitoring device; (ii) patient app; (iii) remote monitoring HCP platform; (iv) HCP pacemaker programmer.	Regulatory - MD HTA/reimbursement - Generally, as a system
2	Multi-manufacturer developed DHTs, each approved as MDs. Brought together and placed together on the market as a system by a single commercial entity and supplied to multiple health systems.	A series of DHTs brought together to create a remote smart clinic platform and designed to enable remote physical exams by clinicians in the patient's home. DHTs would typically include thermometers, stethoscopes, otoscopes, laryngoscope, all integrated through a mobile phone or tablet-based platform ⁵ .	Regulatory - MD HTA/reimbursement - Generally, as a system
3	Multi-manufacturer developed DHTs grouped together with a combination of other MD types, non-MDs, medical IT systems (e.g., EHR), and human digital interactions - e.g. teleconsultation system and doctors. Brought together and placed together on the market as a system by a single commercial entity and supplied to multiple health systems.	A HaH system, including a patient facing app, a clinical dashboard for monitoring patient vitals and alert systems to flag abnormalities, developed by a commercial operator. Platforms include smartphone apps with wearable kits and monitoring devices that are tailored to the patient's care pathway ^{6,7} .	Regulatory - Includes MD, non-MD DHT, and human components. HTA/reimbursement - Generally, as a system
4	Multi-manufacturer developed DHTs grouped together with a combination of other MD types, non-MDs, medical IT systems (e.g., EHR), and human digital interactions - e.g. teleconsultation system and doctors. Brought	Bring Your Own Device or BYOD is a concept gaining some traction where patients can use their own devices like smart phones linked with a medical device for point of care diagnostics or communication of results with their HCP ⁸ .	Regulatory - Includes MD, non-MD DHT and human components. HTA/reimbursement: - Not yet known.

	together automatically, flexibly and dynamically, making use of existing consumer wearables in smartphones, smartwatches and smartphones.		
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